

A hybrid acrylic resin and permanent silicone soft liner prosthesis for a microstomia patient: A case report.

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Abstract

Edentulous patients with compromised ridge and reduced mouth opening may let extra difficulty to the clinician. The rehabilitation of such kind of patient cannot be managed by conventional methods. Various techniques are used to rehabilitate the patient with microstomia. In this article, we are rehabilitating a Hemi-mandibulectomy patient with excessive fibrosis of the cheek after onco-surgery. The patient was rehabilitated by a hybrid prosthesis which was comprised of acrylic and silicone material. The base of the denture was prepared by silicone for easy insertion in the fibrosed oral cavity. The rest of the material in the prosthesis was prepared by acrylic for strength against the masticatory forces.

Keyword: Hemi-mandibulectomy, acrylic, silicones, hybrid prosthesis.

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Submitted: 16-Oct-2021 **Revised:** 24-Oct-2021 **Accepted:** 25-Nov-2021 **Published:** 15-Dec-2021

Introduction

Loss of mandibular continuity following mandibular resection may prove to be a debilitating condition for the patient. Segmental resection of the mandible results in significant physiological and esthetic problems especially due to limited mouth opening (microstomia).^[1] Microstomia causes difficulty in eating as well as speech, thereby reducing the quality of life in the affected individuals. Prosthodontic rehabilitation of such patients can enhance function, speech and esthetics.

Segmental mandibular resection usually rule out the possibility of rehabilitation with dental implants or fixed prosthesis. In this scientific era, one of the most challenging maxillofacial intervention is an endeavor to fabricate a functional complete denture for such patients. The insertion and removal of conventional oral prostheses is demanding for these patients owing to microstomia. Further, prosthetic rehabilitation of these patients by conventional approaches has

proved to be futile. Hence, denture fabrication by traditional techniques should be modified.

First, difficulty in prosthetic rehabilitation starts with the impression making for which flexible and sectioned trays have been proposed.^[2] Sectional-collapsible, only collapsible and only sectional dentures have been fabricated for the prosthodontic treatment of patients with limited intraoral access. In general, a simple hinge, clasp retainers, a swing-lock attachment, cast magnetic attachments, stud attachments and pins and telescope systems can be used to fix the segments of sectional collapsible dentures.^[3-5] Poor manual dexterity limits the usefulness of these attachments in some patients.^[6] Collapsible dentures using flexible denture materials were reported to have limited use due to longevity concerns.^[7] Heat cured acrylic resin and permanent silicone soft liner was employed in the present case report to combine their properties of rigidity and cushioning effect on supporting soft

tissues respectively. Thus, this article describes the fabrication of a hybrid collapsible mandibular denture with heat-cured acrylic resin and permanent silicone soft liner for the prosthetic rehabilitation of a patient suffering from microstomia following segmental mandibulectomy.

Clinical Report

A 71-year-old male patient reported to the Department of Prosthodontics, Institute of Dental Studies and Technologies for functional rehabilitation of his edentulous state. The patient's anamnesis revealed segmental resection of the anterior part of his mandible from the right canine region to left premolar region due to squamous cell carcinoma six years ago. The clinical observation showed Cantor and Curtis class I mandibular defect (radical alveolectomy with preservation of mandibular continuity)⁸. The patient's face was asymmetrical and a bit deviated on the right side. There were no palpable lymphnodes in the head and neck region. Oral examination showed reduced maximum mouth opening measuring approximately 22 mm. Intraoral examination revealed that the tissue bed in the edentulous region was not displaceable. Maxillary teeth were present on both sides from central incisors up to second molars. Only right first (tooth 46) and left second molars (tooth 37) were present in mandibular arch. As the limited mouth opening would propose difficulty in the fabrication of a conventional complete denture, it was decided to fabricate a hybrid collapsible maxillary denture with heat-cured acrylic resin and permanent silicone soft liner.

Preliminary impressions were made with flexible trays with polyvinyl siloxane (PVS) elastomer of putty consistency (Aquasil soft putty/regular set; Dentsply DeTrey, Konstanz, Germany). After trimming the overextended mandibular impression, the secondary impression was made with light-

body PVS impression material (Aquasil LV; Dentsply DeTrey) over the primary impression. Before the initiation of impression making, the teeth 37 and 46 were prepared as overdenture abutments.

The master cast was poured in dental stone (Kalstone; Kalabhai Karson Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India). The temporary record denture base was made of thermoplastic sheet of 2 mm thickness (Star™ Soft Eva Sheets; Andent Pvt. Ltd., Delhi, India), which was used to record the vertical dimension at occlusion and centric relation. The wax rim was fabricated on temporary denture base followed by sectioning of the wax rim in the canine-premolar region for easy insertion into the patient's mouth. Then, jaw relation record was obtained.

The master casts along with the jaw relation record were mounted on a semi-adjustable articulator (Hanau™ Wide-View Arcon Articulator; Whip Mix Corp., Louisville, KY), and the teeth (Cosmo HXL, Dentsply DeTrey) arrangement was done.

The try-in was executed followed by flasking and de-waxing. The thermoplastic resin record base (Star™ Soft Eva Sheets) was cleaned and replaced on the master cast which will act as spacer for a permanent soft liner. The separating medium was applied on the mold (except the teeth) and the master cast. The heat-cured acrylic resin (Lucitone 199 Denture Base Material; Dentsply DeTrey) was packed in dough stage into a lukewarm flask. Prior to pressing, a polyethylene (PE) foil was placed between the acrylic and spacer. This allowed easy separation of flask parts at trial closure. The flask was pressed for 10 to 15 minutes at 100 kp in a hydraulic press. The PE sheet and excess acrylic were removed. A part of acrylic was removed using a blade from 37 and 36 teeth region to create space for the soft liner collar. A slit was made in the canine-premolar region of the acrylic resin before it attained sufficient stiffness to prevent any

deformation during packing of soft liner (Molloplast[®] B, Detax GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) over it. This slit facilitated flexion of the prosthesis for easy insertion and removal from the mouth.

The flask was closed with spacer and PE foil and tightened with a clamp. The flask was placed in water at room temperature which was boiled for approximately 30 minutes which was followed by cooling phase. This prepolymerization process prevented possible reaction of the soft liner with the acrylic monomer along with allowing acrylic resin to gain adequate stiffness. The flask was opened carefully and the PE foil and spacer were removed.

The silicone soft liner was dispensed with a clean spatula from the jar and packed over the prepressed acrylic in the mold. A new PE foil was placed between the permanent soft liner and master cast. The flask was closed again at the same pressure (100 kp). The flask was opened and the excess soft liner along with the PE sheet were removed. The flask was again closed and pressed for approximately 10 to 15 minutes at 100 kp. The tightened flask was placed in cold water and heated slowly to 100°C. The polymerization was done in boiling water at 100°C for approximately 2 hours. The flask was allowed to cool slowly.

The acrylic portion was polished and the excess soft liner was cut. The roughened areas were smoothed and polished with a polishing disc. This definitive hybrid prosthesis is quite collapsible. This collapsible hybrid prosthesis can be easily inserted and removed from the oral cavity even by a patient with limited manual dexterity (e.g. scleroderma patients). After due occlusal adjustments, the prosthesis was delivered to the patient.

Discussion

The cosmetic and functional disability following mandibular resection is significant

and disabling. The restoration of such defects present quite a challenge to the prosthodontist. In treatment planning, efforts are made to preserve as many teeth as possible to augment retention of the prosthesis.

The first difficult step encountered in the fabrication of the prosthesis is the impression making. Rigid stock trays give accurate impression but are difficult to insert. Sectional trays present with the difficulty of reliable orientation with connecting mechanism during impression making and also during pouring cast.^[9] Hence, flexible stock trays were used.

Limited mouth opening hinders joining the segments of a sectional denture intraorally. Hence, we decided to fabricate a collapsible hybrid mandibular denture, combining silicone soft liner and heat-cured acrylic resin. The silicone soft liner (Molloplast B) that was used is a heat-activated silicone. It is available in dough consistency. Heat-activated permanent silicone soft liners have high resilience and increased elasticity.^[10] This enables them to maintain their cushioning effect for a longer period of time. The cushioning effect of the soft liner minimizes the trauma to underlying supporting structures. The usual soft liners have limitation of favoring microorganism growth. Hence, Molloplast B with an anti-plaque effect (according to manufacturer), aids in minimizing plaque deposition.

Despite the limited mouth opening, the patient was able to insert and remove the prosthesis with appropriate ease. The collapsible posterior section of soft liner and the slit created in the acrylic denture base in the canine–premolar region supported the flexibility.^[11] Adequate retention and stability of the prosthesis was also achieved. The patient initially had complaints about difficulty in speaking and chewing, but within 6 to 8 weeks, he was satisfied as reported from the recall visits.

Conclusion

It is often difficult to apply conventional clinical procedures to construct dentures for patients who demonstrate limited mouth opening. This innovative modification of denture fabrication was less demanding for the patient with microstomia both during the fabrication and also while insertion and removal, thereby promoting better function, health, esthetics and overall well being of the patient.

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Figures

Fig 1: Intraoral view- mandibular arch

Fig 4. Teeth arrangement done.

Fig 2: Border moulding done with light body

Fig 5. Flasking and dewaxing done

Fig 3: Pick up impression made with alginate

Fig 6: Part of acrylic was cut from half of the ridge area to create space for the soft liner

Fig 7: Definitive hybrid prosthesis which is quite collapsible

